

Documentation of the GIGAPsych System Prototype

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This document describes the fundamental design of the **GIGAPsych** system, as a prototype of a comprehensive online repository designed to facilitate **open collaboration** (open science) and **open data** standardization in psychological research. The system allows researchers to upload, share, and merge pseudonymized raw datasets, aiming to create a comprehensive "Giga database" for the psychological sciences. Therefore the project directly addresses current challenges in psychological research conducted by various teams across the world where data is fragmented, stored in various formats, and often unsuitable for automated merging. GIGAPsych introduces machine-readable codebook standards to solve the problem of interoperability as well as data maintenance and handling for building larger datasets for fostering psychological research based on open science and open data standards.

System Architecture

The prototype of GIGAPsych system follows a modern, scalable architecture designed for security and interoperability, built on open standards, that includes:

- Frontend that is built with React (Next.js) using TypeScript. It utilizes Zod for schema validation and Tailwind CSS for the interface.
- Backend as a Spring Boot (Java) which is a monolithic application following the Backend-for-Frontend (BFF) pattern to streamline communication with the client app.

- Database PostgreSQL, chosen as an open standard known for its reliability in handling relational research data.
- Infrastructure with a Jenkins-based CI/CD pipeline for automated deployment using Docker containers.

A modular monolithic architecture was chosen since this approach is optimal for the prototype phase, ensuring ease of deployment and testing while maintaining code cleanliness, which will allow for a potential migration to reliable microservices in the future that allows scalability and reliability in the long term maintenance and development of the service.

The application backend is built on the Spring Boot framework that provides a layered architecture based on controller, service, repository, and DTO. Security is provided by integration with Spring Security and the OAuth2 protocol. Dependency management makes use of the well known Maven standard.

The system frontend is based on Next.js and React, a well-established standard for online application development. In particular the user interface utilizes the Next.js framework, providing server-side rendering (SSR) that improves performance alongside with BFF (Backend-for-Frontend) provided by Next.js that acts as an intermediary, increasing security (hiding API keys, session management).

Data Management & Standards (DMP)

In alignment with the Data Management Plan, the system adheres to the following principles:

- FAIR Principles - data and software are designed to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR4RS).
- Standardization - use of machine-readable codebooks to enable the automated reading and merging of disparate datasets.
- Data Preservation - pseudonymized research source data is stored on servers ensuring availability for academic verification and identification.

- Privacy - project strictly adherence to GDPR. Only pseudonymized data is accepted, and access is restricted to verified academic researchers through a data sharing agreement.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) of the system provides appropriate data classification. In particular the system processes two main types of files: source datasets (.csv, .xlsx formats) alongside corresponding codebooks that include metadata describing variables, scales, and response keys. Data lifecycle in the prototype system is divided into three major stages: ingestion, where the user uploads a file, validation by the administrator, where the compliance check with the format is provided alongside an anonymization check (ensuring no personal data is present) and storage where the data is stored in a database. As for the security and GDPR, in accordance with the DMP, the system emphasizes pseudonymization, that means data identifying research participants must not be uploaded as well as access control – only verified researchers from academic institutions have full access to the prototype system database.

Key Functional Modules

The prototype of the GIGAPsych system covers key functionality modules related to the following functional areas:

- Authentication supports traditional login and SSO for researcher verification.
- Dataset handling that allows uploading data files with automated mapping to research Instruments covered by the system.
- Academic Moderation (Admin) Panel that covers a multi-step workflow where administrators (designed and trusted researchers) must verify users and approve datasets before they become public.
- Communication: A REST-based internal chat system for coordination between researchers and system moderators.

User Management supports various levels of system users with corresponding privileges. Unverified users can browse general statistics and general information of the system. Registered and verified users, that is researchers with a confirmed

affiliation and credibility have permissions to upload, merge and download data. Admins are seasoned and trusted researchers responsible for data and content moderation as well as account verification. Instrument management mechanism includes a dictionary of standard psychological questionnaires. Administrators can add new definitions, which then serve as templates for data upload and merge.

Software Management Plan and Sustainability (SMP)

Software management sustainability covers crucial areas related to:

- **Licensing** - the software is open-source, licensed under **Apache 2.0**, promoting reuse within the scientific community.
- **Quality Assurance and Testing** - the prototype targets both unit and integration tests to ensure stability.
- **FAIR Principles** - system prototype follows the principles of FAIR.

As for licensing and compliance with open science and open software principles the prototype code is available under the Apache 2.0 license. This supports scientific transparency and allows the researcher community to adapt the system. The quality assurance makes use of both unit tests (based on JUnit and Mockito on the backend) as well as integration tests for verifying the correctness of file uploads. Moreover the system prototype makes use of CI/CD for automated testing via Jenkins. The FAIR Strategy is realised by indexing the metadata in the relational database (findability), accessing the data by REST API (accessibility), use of common open JSON format for codebooks (interoperability) and open-source licensing (reusability).

Conclusions and Further Development Towards AI-based system

As a prototype, GIGAPsych proves that the automated integration of psychological data is possible using machine-readable metadata and in the future also with AI support. At the prototype stage preliminary AI-based concepts were verified. In particular in the prototype stage artificial intelligence modules were implemented as

a preliminary limited concept and technological trial, rather than a fully autonomous feature. The tests were based on Gemini 2.5-flash-lite as a research module integrated for investigating the potential of automated assistance in the metadata mapping process. In particular during the research part of the project the preliminary concept was verified that AI may suggest how columns in uploaded files (.csv, .xlsx) should be mapped to established psychological instruments and variables. Those preliminary results are the subject of further investigation and development as a part of the human-in-the-loop approach where an AI on-premise model may be developed and deployed to support manual processes by suggesting a certainty level of the processed data and provide clues for the supervision by the researchers administrating the system to be reviewed and confirmed by them before the data is processed. The use of AI may significantly speed up the traditional manual process of data verification and merging in the future system.